

8T – Multiverse Uncertainties

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the 8T, author will present a set of uncertainties which are features of the main ideas. In contrast to other physical theories which correlate uncertainties to conjugate variables, such as momenta and position, author will present a broader set of uncertainties which go beyond the conjugate relation, and are considered by the 8T author as integral features of nature itself.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equation (1) By (1.2A) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

Now the subject of the paper is the following. What is the nature of nature in terms of certainty. Despite 8T is able to put under one equation some of the major questions of modern physics, such as dark energy, flatness and dark matter, which are direct results of the multiverse as presented in (2.1. A) and (2.1. B), how much can we predict really? 8T can predict the coupling magnitudes and all the numbers nature will ever generate, which is a significant step forward. At the same time, there are many uncertainties, which go beyond the conjugate relation of QM, which famously known between momenta and position or time and energy. The first uncertainty is the uncertainty of decays. Given higher term coupling, The Boson can be represented as a nested Boson, composed of lower primes. It is impossible to derive which combination is serving the actual decay, and the higher the coupling the larger the possible combinations of Bosonic decays. The idea is presented in page one hundred forty seven in the 8T thesis. The second uncertainty revolves around the arbitrary variation term (1.48) which vanish onto matter. It is impossible, as far as one can see, to derive the amount of matter being created at each moment, nor it is possible to derive where those arbitrary variations will appear, that can only be done in retrospective, where stars and galaxies are at. These are two major uncertainties. It is also impossible to estimate how fast those arbitrary variations form into matter, what is the time segment, is it same for all or varying according to the surface and the amount of matter that was already there?

A third uncertainty is regarding the matter configuration on other universes, it is not possible to predict the configuration, the rate or the position of matter on other universes, other than stating that the matter on those manifolds is identical to matter on our own manifold, skeleton wise, i.e. Quarks.

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g_m - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g_n = 0 \quad (2.1.B)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \delta g_i \rightarrow \mathcal{R}^{s_1} \in [0,1]$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \delta g_i \rightarrow \mathcal{R}^{s_2} \in [0,1]$$

$$\mathcal{R}^{s_1} \neq \mathcal{R}^{s_2}$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \delta g_i \equiv \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \delta g_i$$

The last uncertainty is the uncertainty of class. We **assumed** that the heredity condition, which state newborn manifolds will belong to the same class but that is not proven. We also assumed that the families on other manifolds will have the exact same families in terms of total mass, given by the Quark masses pattern, which in contrast to the primorial, took the measured values and used them to define the pattern, where in the primorial the measured values were derived from a variational principle. The other universes have the same form of matter in terms of the kind, i.e. Quarks, but are the masses identical? Is there a principle involved which guarantees those numbers will form? To examine those assumptions a civilization could have two options: The first is to find the principals involved which the kind of manifolds arise, and the numbers of the masses arise, **without measurement**. The principles than must match the measurement, the second is to jump across the packet and measure the traits of matter on each distinct manifold. We assumed that nature is Lagrangian oriented, and generate the minimal number of laws, minimal kind of manifolds and minimal sets of distinct fermion masses, but it is just an educated guess after all.

In contrast to the invariance of the prime ring that ensures that the same Bosons will appear at the same order, the Fermion and manifold classes is still requires work. That picture indicate that at least part of the laws of nature are identical across the multiverse, the same coupling constants will appear at all, matter and Quarks will appear at all, leptons will appear at all the same way. All universes will contain galaxies, and will be flat. However, are they all of the same kind? Are the Fermions masses identical for all?

Finding out the principle in which the specific masses arise from a variational principle identical to primorial, and this specific class of manifold arise from all potential classes of manifolds, could be the biggest challenge facing modern theoretical physics, and the last pillar to reach the completion of the unified theory, 8T. At the current stage, the theory is able to explain the major what's and one of the two major whys, the why of the coupling magnitudes,. The "why" which still requires work is the "why" of those masses. What is the variational principle leading to those numbers? Is there one at all?

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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